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Factors Influencing Brand Switching in Mobile Telecommunication Industry in Bangladesh

Anup Kumar Mandal*

Department of Economics and Sociology, Patuakhali Science and Technology University, Dumki, Patuakhali, Bangladesh.

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Abstract

Today telecommunications industry is a key indicator of productivity across economies and societies. In recent times, developing nations have witnessed significant transformation within this sector due to the impact it has had on their economies. Higher the degree of competitiveness among the brands available to the consumers, higher would be the intensity of brand switching. This research has been conducted in order to examine the factors influencing brand switching in mobile telecommunication industry in Bangladesh. Qualitative and quantitative methods have been developed a strong base of research. Primary data for research has been collected through an interview schedule from 80 mobile subscribers in Bangladesh. Data were coded and analyzed by using SPSS and Excel. The results of research suggest that service charge is the most influential factor on brand switching in telecommunication sector. Other factors that have been found influential factor on brand switching were poor customer care service of previous operator, occupation and economic circumstances, switching cost, better service availability, wide and strong network. So the mobile operator and other related agencies should provide better service to the customers for reducing brand switching of mobile telecommunication industry in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Mobile telecommunication industry; Brand switching; Influential factor; Service charge; Customers service

1 Introduction

The telecommunication industry is one of the most important industries of the world. The telecommunication industry in Bangladesh has scaled up rapidly over beyond decade having a complete of 176.94 million active subscription on the end of July 2021. Subscriber means the biometric verified subscribers/subscriptions that have any activity (voice, data, sms etc.) at least once in the preceding 90 days ⁽¹⁾. In order to gain competitive advantage as competition is getting more and more intense, the companies are compelled to innovate and do their best for the customer satisfaction. As in the telecom industry the customers have multiple choices to select among service providers and actively seek their rights of switching from one telecom service provider to another. In this ferocious competition customers requires better services at reasonable prices, while service providers concentrating on retention of the most profitable customers instead of acquisition.

But due to intense competition in telecommunication industry customers frequently switch from one service provider to another. ⁽²⁾ identified that brand switching is the process in which consumer switches from the usage of one product to another product but of same category. Brand switching behavior of customers differs in different industries. Some industries are characterized by high brand switching rates while others show low rates of brand switching. Telecommunication industry is one of the industries which possess high rates of brand switching ⁽³⁾. However according to ^(4, 5, 6, 7) found that price is the most important factor which influences consumer purchase decision. ⁽⁸⁾ Explained the importance of net quality, service quality, leverage, coverage voice clarity etc. ^(9, 10, 11, 12). emphasized that service quality

* Corresponding author: Anup Kumar Mandal

is considered a positive driver for behavior intention of leaving, switching or retaining. Besides ⁽¹³⁾ identified seven factors which affect customer's service switching behavior in his model. Among those seven factors he gave priority upon price, inconvenience, and core service failure factor. ⁽¹⁴⁾ found that customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is a potentially important factors for brand switching. However ^(15, 16, 17) asserted that switching barrier plays the role of an adjustment variable in the interrelationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. ^(18, 19) identifies the significance of customer loyalty as it closely relates to the company's continued survival, and future growth. But ⁽²⁰⁾ conclude that factors affecting customers brand switching in mobile telecommunication industry was price, inconvenience, service failure and factors were creating barriers to customers brand switching in mobile telecommunication industry. Although a good number of researches have been done on the factors affecting brand switching of telecommunication industry in other country, few studies have been done in Bangladesh. Considering this factors influencing brand switching of mobile telecommunication industry in Bangladesh was favored and selected for the present study. The present study is an addition of more information and broad area analysis of factors influencing brand switching in mobile telecommunication industry in Bangladesh. The study identifies the factors affecting switching behavior of mobile telecommunication service user in Bangladesh.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample design, distribution and collection of responses

The study was conducted in Bangladesh and had chosen the sample size of 80 general people of various aged. They are selected from various place of Bangladesh. Fifty percent (50%) respondents were men and fifty (50%) percent were women. Respondents were divided in four aged group i.e. a) less than 20 years b) 21-30 years c) 31-40 years d) above 40 years. The study also collected information from them equally i.e. 10 respondents was selected for every aged group. Among those respondents students, housewife, service provider, graduate and retired person were considered. In order to control common method biases, it was assured to respondents that there was no right or wrong answers and they should provide answer as honestly as possible and no information will be shared with other person or organization. It has been also assured that the respondents' identity will not be disclosed i.e. as like answers to be anonymous and the information of this survey will be used for researchers' academic purpose.

2.2 Preparation of interview schedule

The primary data was collected by survey method through interview schedule. The interview schedule was designed according to the existing literatures and experts' opinions. Some items were directly adopted from previous survey instrument to operationalize the constructs in this study. Few new items also included in different constructs to get good response from data collection through survey. The interview schedule has three parts. The first part was intended to understand the personal information of respondents using nominal scale. The second part is consists the general information of their mobile phone operator and switched time of operators. The third part is consists of factors that affect their switching behavior.

2.3 Scaling technique

The perceptions of respondents were regarding the constructs of the model. The questionnaire consists of different questions. All constructs were measured using multiple items by a five point Likert scale (1= strongly disagree, 2= disagree, 3= sometimes agree, 4= agree, and 5= strongly agree).

2.4 Data Analysis Method

The study used Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16.0 for data entry and analysis. Results obtained from the data analysis on SPSS and Excel. The results consist of case processing summary, correlation, regression analysis and factor analysis.

2.5 Hypothesis

In order to check the nature of relationship between dependent and independent variables, following hypothesis were purposed.

- H_0 : Service charge hasn't any significant impact on brand switching in the telecom industry.
- H_0 : There isn't significant relationship between reliability (untrusted other operator) and consumer switching behavior.
- H_0 : Sales Promotions haven't significant impact on brand switching in the telecom industry.

- H_0 : There isn't significant relationship between customer services and consumer switching behavior.
- H_0 : There isn't a significant relationship between service quality and consumer switching behavior.
- H_0 : Network Quality hasn't any significant impact on brand switching in the telecom industry.
- H_0 : There isn't any significant relationship between Low SMS & call rates and consumer switching behavior.
- H_0 : Available new offer of operators don't influences customer to switch operator.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Hypothesis

There are two hypothesis 1) Null Hypothesis 2) Alternative Hypothesis. A null hypothesis is a statement of the status quo, one of no difference or no effect. If the null hypothesis is not rejected, no change will be made. An alternative hypothesis is one in which some difference or effect is expected. Accepting the alternative hypothesis will lead to change in opinion or actions.

Thus the alternative hypothesis is the opposite of the null hypothesis.

3.1.1 H_0 : Service charge hasn't any significant impact on brand switching in the telecom industry.

$$H1: \mu > 2.5$$

$$N = 80$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{X} = 4.5750$$

$$\sigma = .85351$$

$$Z \text{ cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 21.7448$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z \text{ cal} > Z \text{ tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it can be said that the service charge affect for brand switching on customer.

3.1.2 H_0 : There isn't significant relationship between reliability (consistency of good services) and consumer switching behavior.

$$H1: \mu > 2.5$$

$$N = 80$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{X} = 3.6750$$

$$\sigma = .75933$$

$$Z \text{ cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 13.84$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z \text{ cal} > Z \text{ tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it can be said that there have a significant relationship between reliability (consistency of good services) and consumer switching behavior.

3.1.3 H_0 : Sales Promotions haven't significant impact on brand switching in the telecom industry.

$$H1: \mu > 2.5$$

$$N = 80$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{X} = 3.8875$$

$$\sigma = .92769$$

$$Z \text{ cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 13.3783$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z_{cal} > Z_{tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it can be said that sales promotion of operator influences customer to switch one to another operator.

3.1.4 **H_0** : *There isn't significant relationship between customer services and consumer switching behavior.*

$$H_1: \mu > 2.5$$

$$N = 80$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{X} = 2.8125$$

$$\sigma = .50551$$

$$Z_{cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 5.5292$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z_{cal} > Z_{tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it clears that the customer service of operator affects customer brand switching.

3.1.5 **H_0** : *There isn't a significant relationship between service quality and consumer switching behavior.*

$$H_1: \mu > 2.5$$

$$N = 80$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{X} = 3.5250$$

$$\sigma = .72871$$

$$Z_{cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 12.58$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z_{cal} > Z_{tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it can be said that there is a significant relationship between service quality and consumer switching behavior.

3.1.6 **H_0** : *Network Quality hasn't any significant impact on brand switching in the telecom industry.*

$$H_1: \mu > 2.5$$

$$N = 80$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{X} = 4.30$$

$$\sigma = .60379$$

$$Z_{cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 26.66$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z_{cal} > Z_{tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it can be said that the network quality influence customer on their switching decision.

3.1.7 **H_0** : *There isn't any significant relationship between Low SMS & call rates and consumer switching behavior.*

$$H_1: \mu > 2.5$$

$$N = 80$$

$$\text{Here } \bar{X} = 4.5500$$

$$\sigma = .76141$$

$$Z_{cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 29.36$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z_{cal} > Z_{tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it's clear that customer switches their service operator on the basis of SMS and call rate.

3.1.8 H_0 : Available new offer of operators don't influences customer to switch operator.

H_1 : $\mu > 2.5$

$N = 80$

Here $\bar{X} = 4.025$

$\sigma = .92743$

$$Z_{cal} = (\bar{X} - \mu) / (\sigma / \sqrt{n}) = 14.70$$

At 5% level of significance, the value of Z-Distribution table is: $Z_{0.05} = 1.645$. Since $Z_{cal} > Z_{tab}$, the null hypothesis is rejected. So at 5% level of significance, it can be said that the available new offer of operators influences customer to switch operator.

3.2 Regression

Regression analysis is a powerful and flexible procedure for analyzing associative relationships between a metric dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It is concerned with the nature and degree of association between variables and does not imply or assume any causality. It is used in the following ways: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$

Table 1 Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.663	4.323		0.385	0.702
Employers/friends/family influence	-0.046	0.138	-0.053	-0.334	0.739
Personality and self-concept	-0.484	0.241	-0.292	-2.008	0.049
lifestyle and values	-0.244	0.204	-0.166	-1.194	0.237
Occupation and economic circumstances	0.437	0.230	0.244	1.903	0.032
Poor company image and popularity	-0.407	0.371	-0.161	-1.098	0.277
Role and status	-0.425	0.647	-0.178	-0.657	0.514
Poor network coverage	0.750	0.798	0.484	0.940	0.351
Innovativeness of current operator	-1.101	1.179	-0.565	-0.934	0.354
Lower service quality	0.603	0.515	0.297	1.169	0.247
Poor customer care service of previous operator	0.562	1.354	0.224	0.415	0.000
High service charge	-0.083	0.998	-0.056	-0.084	0.000
Hidden charge	-0.146	0.373	-0.100	-0.391	0.000
Switching cost	0.422	0.199	0.430	2.121	0.037

Unavailability/ rarity of new offers	-0.321	1.224	-0.234	-0.262	0.000
New offer of current operator	-0.546	0.560	-0.449	-0.975	0.000
Influencing advertisement of current operator	0.010	0.223	0.008	0.046	0.963
Low price of SIM	-0.094	0.795	-0.070	-0.118	0.906
Low service charge	-0.344	0.702	-0.207	-0.491	0.625
Cash back or bonus on use and recharge	-0.741	0.684	-0.443	-1.084	0.283
Low call charge facility in intra network	0.495	0.486	0.269	1.020	0.312
Everyone knows this number	0.277	0.387	0.352	0.714	0.478
Untrusted others operator	-1.081	1.812	-0.364	-0.597	0.553
Brand image and popularity	-0.813	0.963	-0.321	-0.844	0.402
Better service availability	0.641	1.080	0.383	0.593	0.000
Faster internet service	0.264	0.136	0.316	1.940	0.047
Better customer care service	-0.269	0.727	-0.161	-0.371	0.000
SIM no portability	-0.222	1.586	-0.043	-0.140	0.889
Miscellaneous serviceable facilities	0.568	0.920	0.237	0.617	0.540
Wide and strong network	0.658	0.489	0.313	1.348	0.000
Innovativeness and available new offer of current operator	0.138	0.235	0.094	0.568	0.000
Easy and convenient recharge facility	-0.517	0.903	-0.318	-0.573	0.000
Cash back or bonus on use and recharge	0.116	0.364	0.093	0.320	0.223
Dependent Variable: times of changing operator from the using mobile phone					

3.2.1 Step 1 They have valid relationship with dependent variable because significance level is fewer than 5%.

Table 2 Significance level

	Variables	Significance level
1	Poor customer care service of previous operator	0.000
2	Personality and self-concept	0.049
3	Occupation and economic circumstances	0.032
4	High service charge	0.000
5	Hidden charge	0.000
6	Switching cost	0.037
7	Unavailability/ rarity of new offers	0.000
8	New offer of current operator	0.000
9	Influencing advertisement of current operator	0.000
10	Better service availability	0.000
11	Faster internet service	0.047

12	Better customer care service	0.000
13	Wide and strong network	0.000
14	Innovativeness and available new offer of current operator	0.000
15	Easy and convenient recharge facility	0.000

3.2.2 **Step 2:** *Bivariate Regression Model: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n$*

Y= Dependent or criterion variable

X= Independent or predictor value

$Y = 1.663 + (\text{poor customer care service of previous operator}) 0.562 + (\text{personality and self-concept}) -0.484 + (\text{occupation and economic circumstances}) 0.437 + (\text{high service charge}) -0.083 + (\text{hidden charge}) -0.146 + (\text{switching cost}) 0.422 + (\text{unavailability/ rarity of new offers}) -0.321 + (\text{new offer of current operator}) -0.546 + (\text{influencing advertisement of current operator}) 0.010 + (\text{better service availability}) 0.641 + (\text{faster internet service}) 0.264 + (\text{better service availability}) 0.641 + (\text{better customer care service}) -0.269 + (\text{wide and strong network}) 0.658 + (\text{innovativeness and available new offer of current operator}) 0.138 + (\text{easy and convenient recharge facility}) -0.517$

3.2.3 **Step 3** *Among all independent variables following variables have more strength than others variables.*

Table 3 Relationship level of variables

	Variables	Strength relationship
1	Poor customer care service of previous operator	0.562
2	Personality and self-concept	-0.484
3	Occupation and economic circumstances	0.437
4	High service charge	-0.083
5	Hidden charge	-0.146
6	Switching cost	0.422
7	Unavailability/ rarity of new offers	-0.321
8	New offer of current operator	-0.546
9	Influencing advertisement of current operator	0.010
10	Better service availability	0.641
11	Faster internet service	0.264
12	Better customer care service	-0.269
13	Wide and strong network	0.658
14	Innovativeness and available new offer of current operator	0.138
15	Easy and convenient recharge facility	-0.517

3.2.4 **Step 4:** *From the regression equation it is clear that if 1 unit of wide and strong network increase, which the independent variable in this study is, there will be a 0.658 unit increase in brand switching.*

3.3 Factor analysis

Factor Analysis is a general name denoting a class of procedures primarily used for data reduction and summarization. It is an interdependence technique in that an entire set of interdependent relationships is examined.

Model:

$$X_i = A_{i1}F_1 + A_{i2}F_2 + A_{i3}F_3 + \dots + A_{im}F_m + V_iU_i$$

3.3.1 *KMO and Bartlett's Test*

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy is an index used to examine the appropriateness of factor analysis. High values (between 0.5-1.0) indicate factor analysis is appropriate. Values below 0.5 imply that factor analysis may not be appropriate. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity is a test statistic used to examine the hypothesis that the variables are uncorrelated in the population.

Table 4 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.506
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	98.748	98.748
	15	15
	0.000	0.000

In this table (Table 4), Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy is 0.506 which is above 50% and it is reasonably supporting the appropriateness of using factor analysis.

In the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity significance is 0.000 which is below 5% and it is appropriate.

3.4 Determine the number of factor

It is possible to compute as many principal components as there are variables, but in doing so tough, no parsimony is gained. In order to summarize the information contained to the original variables, a smaller no of factors should be extracted. Several procedures have been suggested for determining the factor.

3.4.1 *Determination based on eigenvalues*

In this approach, only factors with eigenvalues greater than 1.0 are retained; the other factors are not included in the model. An eigenvalues represents the amount of variance associated with the factor. Only factors with a variance greater than 1.0 are included.

3.4.2 *Determination based on percentage of variance*

In this approach, the no of factors extracted is determined so that the cumulative percentage of variance extracted by the factors reaches a satisfactory level. What level of variance is satisfactory depends upon the problem. However it is recommended that the factors extracted should account for at least 60% of the variance.

Table 5 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	1.981	33.018	33.018	1.981	33.018	33.018
2	1.622	27.041	60.060	1.622	27.041	60.060
3	0.364	16.748	76.808			
4	0.592	9.859	86.667			
5	0.530	8.831	95.497			
6	0.270	4.503	100.000			

In this table (Table 5), initial eigenvalues of two components is above 1. So, the study can extract two factors from the table. From percentage of variance it can be said that the study can extract two factors from the table (Table 5). In the first component percentage of variance is 33.018 and in second component percentage of variance is 27.041, and two account for 60.060.

3.5 Component matrix

The factor matrix contains the coefficients used to express the standardized variables. The initial or unrotated factor matrix indicates the relationship between the factors and individual variables. The coefficients of the factor matrix can be used to interpret the factors.

Table 6 Component Matrix

	Component	
	1	2
Poor customer care service of previous operator	0.368	-0.475
Occupation and economic circumstances	0.014	0.456
Switching cost	0.657	-0.611
Better service availability	0.665	0.169
Wide and strong network	0.881	0.049
High service charge	0.307	0.154

The results of Table 6 found that if one value is above 0.3, and another is under 0.3, then it will fall under component 1 or 2.

Table 7 No. of Factors

Factor-1 (Economic factor)		Factor-2 (Performance and technological factor)	
Occupation and economic circumstances	0.456	Poor customer care service of previous operator	0.368
Switching cost	0.657	Better service availability	0.665
High service charge	0.307	Wide and strong network	0.881
Total	1.42	Total	1.914

Between these two factors, factor-2 is more important than factor-1 (Table 7). Because the total value of factor-2 is greater than the value of factor-1 and the wide and strong network is more influential to switch the operator than other variables. So the study found that there were six factors which influence consumers' cell phone operators' choice decisions: those are poor customer care service of previous operator, occupation and economic circumstances, switching cost, better service availability, wide and strong network, high service charge. These were shorted by two factors that were economic factor and performance and technological factor. So the operator should consider their network system's strength to increase their business profitability and market share.

4 Conclusion

The telecommunication services in Bangladesh have witnessed the phenomenal change over the last few years. The craze for mobile services in Bangladesh is increasing substantially. Mobile communication technology has brought tremendous change in day-to-day activities of common people to entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. Cellular phone networks have been coming up with new features every day. Keeping the high consumers demand into consideration, many local and multinational companies have launched their services in the market. An innovation is happening in the mobile network technology every day. Contrary to the introduction years of mobile phone, today it has been used by almost all age groups, and by both males and females, and the gap between age groups and the gap between males and females with respect to mobile phone usage/ownership has been decreased. Rapid growth of customers makes the market more vulnerable and turbulent. Companies are trying to make profit and even survive in a highly competitive environment. So, it becomes extremely important to learn customers' desired expectation and the factors that are influencing consumers' purchase decisions. According to this study, the customers are more interested to have their brand with reasonable cost and with good network. The customers need to know frequently about the various facilities that the

company is providing and about the new schemes that they offer through advertisement, SMS, calls, etc. The cellular phone service providers can provide the customers good quality network to make the customer use the same network all through their life. The cellular phone service providers could facilitate the immediate service to the request, suggested by the customers. Also the company could introduce new schemes to attract them. If all these would happen, then the cellular phone network may prevent or minimize brand switching. It can be concluded that if any service provider wants to be successful longer period of time then it has to provide better service for customers.

References

- [1] BRTC. 2021. Mobile Phone subscribers in Bangladesh. Available at <http://www.btrc.gov.bd/content/mobile-phone-subscribers-bangladesh-july-2021>. accessed on 26 September 2021.
- [2] Kumar, R. R. and Charlas, D. L. 2011. Brand switching in cellular phone service industry because of bill-related issues faced by clients. 1(5).
- [3] Ross, I., Gustafsson, A. and Edvardsson, B. 2004. "The role of customer clubs in recent telecom relationship". *European Journal of Marketing*.
- [4] Kollmann, T. 2000. The price/acceptance function: perspectives of a pricing policy in European telecommunication markets. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 3(1), 7-15.
- [5] Sathish, M., Santhosh, K., Naveen, K. J. and Jeevanantham, V. 2011. "A Study on Consumer Switching Behaviour in Cellular Service Provider: A Study with reference to Chennai," *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business*, Far East Research Centre, vol. 2(5), pages 71-81.
- [6] Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. 2010, *Principles of Marketing*. 13th Edition., New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- [7] Singh, M., and Bansal, S. 2019. Factors influencing brand switching behaviour among Indian youth: An empirical study of mobile service providers. *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, April-June, 6(2):98-100.
- [8] Ashraf, R. U., Saeed, D. R., Arshad, D. H. M., Zaidi, S. A. H., Ahmad, W. 2013. Determinants of customer satisfaction: The case of Pakistan telecommunication industry. *J Basic Appl Res*. 3(1):251-8.
- [9] Venetis, K. A., and Ghauri, P. N. 2000. The importance of service quality on customer retention: An empirical study of business service relationships (pp. 215-224). *Proceedings of the Marketing in a Global Economy Conference*, Buenos Aires.
- [10] Serkan, A., and Gorhan, O. 2004. The analysis of antecedents of customer loyalty in Turkish mobile telecommunication markets. *Eur J Marketing*. 39:910-25.
- [11] Fuha, M. 2005. Dynamics of price sensitivity among mobile service customers. *J Product and Brand Manag*. 14(1):65-73.
- [12] Kabir. 2009. The factors determining customer satisfaction and loyalty: Study of mobile telecommunication industry in Bangladesh, *ASA University Review*. 3(2):147-56.
- [13] Keaveney, S. M. 1995. Customer switching behavior in service industries: An exploratory study. *The Journal of Marketing*, 71-82.
- [14] Jones, M. A., Mothersbaugh, D. L., and Beatty, S. E. 2000. Switching barriers and repurchase intentions in services. *Journal of retailing*, 76(2), 259-274.
- [15] Colgate, M., and Lang, B. 2001. Switching barriers in consumer markets: an investigation of the financial services industry. *Journal of consumer marketing*, 18(4), 332-347.
- [16] Jones, M. A., Mothersbaugh, D. L., & Beatty, S. E. (2002). Why customers stay: measuring the underlying dimensions of services switching costs and managing their differential strategic outcomes. *Journal of business research*, 55(6), 441-450
- [17] Lee, M., and Cunningham, L. F. 2001. A cost/benefit approach to understanding service loyalty. *Journal of services Marketing*, 15(2), 113-130.
- [18] Fornell, C., and Wernerfelt, B. 1987. Defensive marketing strategy by customer complaint management: a theoretical analysis. *Journal of Marketing research*, 337-346.
- [19] Ahmad, R., and Buttle, F. 2002. Customer retention management: A reflection of theory and practice. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 20(3), 149-161.
- [20] Masud-Ul-Hasan, M. 2014. Factors Affecting Customers Brand Switching Behavior in Mobile Telecommunication Industry: A Study of Pabna District in Bangladesh. *Asian Business Consortium*, 125-130.